

A Comparative Study of Educational Status of Women in Ancient and Modern India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Zubaidunisa, SM. "A Comparative Study of Educational Status of Women in Ancient and Modern India." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 259–65.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586447>

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Abstract

Women comprises nearly half of the population in our country, but the social discrimination is exist in all perspective irrespective of religion, caste, community, age, place and state etc. women plays a restricted role of a home maker that means mother and wives. women receive only small share of the development opportunities. For improving living status of women, education plays a significant role. Educated women are capable of bringing socio-economic changes. According to the census data 2011, the literacy rate of women is 60.6% which is lower than men literacy rate 81.3%. Thus objective of this paper is to discuss the education status of women during ancient and modern India. It also specifies, importance of women education, the government and many non-government organizations took a lot of projects to spread women education.

“A little knowledge that acts is worth more than much knowledge that is inactive... Knowledge the object of knowledge and application of knowledge- all the three are equally important for motivating to take a wise action”

Introduction

The situation in India in regard to women's status is completely different when compared to that of other countries. It is a known fact that, all over the world 50% of population comprises of women. But in our country; due to the stigma of begetting a female child, there is a great decrease in ratio of women on the basis of sex selection abortion. Though the Indian society ascertains the equal status of men and women in most of the written records or law; very little is practice in reality. Therefore the situation of decreasing sex ratio of male to female paves a way to unequal social status of women with men in India, whereas in western countries women are equal with men. It is evident from our culture that at one side we treat woman as goddess in the form of Lakshmi, Saraswati, Durga and very next movement all the dreadful and illegal breaches being committed against them like rape, sexual harassment, workplace exploitation, kidnapping, 'Female Foeticide and female trafficking'. On the other hand, we can say that everybody treats them like a slave who work without any wages.

Today as per our Constitution we provide equal status to women on the basis of equality principle. This came into light due to the long struggle that women have been experiencing over the past years. Our ancient era is the witness of this inequality, for example Draupadi, wife of five Pandavas was, used by them on the game of dice like goods. Women were also used as court dancers to please the kings and other male members of the royal family, women were not given right to speak loudly in home or public places, these are some cases which shows that in ancient period women were not being treated equally with men. Even she was not allowed to participate freely in economic, social, political and personal activities.

But in the wake of 20th century Mahatma Gandhi started national movement for liberalization of woman. During that time only Rajaram Mohan Roy, Ishwarchandra Vidyasagar and many other social activist started a movement for education of woman, prevention of sati system, restraint of polygamy marriages etc. which were passed in the Parliament and action was taken for Sati prevention, Restrain of child marriages, Equal rights of woman in property and remarriages of widow etc.

After the independence of India, Parliament had made sufficient effort to give equal status to woman with men by removing inequality. For fulfillment of this purpose they have also created a firm by making enactment for Hindu Marriages which define the age for marriage, prevent polygamy and make monogamy marriages mandatory. They have also implemented adoption laws so that any men or women competent to adopt the child and also make laws for maintenance to wife, children, parents etc. Through Constitution of India they have also protected equality of women under article 14, 15, 15(3), 25, 42, 26, 51 (A) (E). In this way the Government on their level makes sufficient efforts to remove inequality of women with men by providing equal status. Till today situation is as it is or we can say that, it becomes worse by committing crime of 'Female Foeticide' which results in to decreasing rate of women in society.

The occurrence of offences of 'Female Foeticide' and Infanticide is deeply rooted in ancient culture which results into death on the basis of sex selection. The most important thing is that, the crime rate of commission of these offences is in the two largest countries in universe much high, i.e. India another is China and it's very disgraceful for our society. It shows the low status of woman in these countries. It is malicious and harsh demonstration against woman by the patriarchal supportive society.

In this way status of woman has been changed from ancient time to modern age. But still 'Female Foeticide' and Infanticide are committed frequently in India and other countries. Therefore, researcher in this research has discussed the position of woman from primitive society to modern society which will help to find out reasons of 'Female Foeticide'.

Women Education in Ancient India

The general position of women in ancient India was unique. The customs of child marriage and enforced widowhood were not prevalent in Vedic India. It is surprising to not that Women enjoyed high status and independence in the society like an unmarried young learned daughter ought to be married to a learned bridegroom. Girls could freely choose their husbands. Early marriage was not in vogue in those days.

Women in ancient India had free access to education. They were expected to participate in Vedic sacrifices and utter mantras. Even some of the hymns of the Rigveda were composed by poetesses. We get references of such learned ladies as Visvavara, Lopamudra, Apala, Urvashi, Ghosa, Sulabha, Lilabati, Maitreyi, Saswati, Kshana, Gargi and others. Maitreyi, the celebrated wife of the most learned philosopher of ancient India, Yajnavalka, used to hold discussion on abstruse philosophical questions with her husband.

Gargi also participated in debate with Yajnavalka on philosophical issues. Lilabati was a great mathematician of ancient India. Thus we find that ancient society was not conservative to provide education to women and that many of them attained to great proficiencies in learning. The ancient women had equal rights with men in respect of education

The Upanayana (Vedic initiation) of girls should have been as common as that of boys. In the Vedic period the women not only enjoyed privileged position but also possessed high standard of morality. They had contributed positively to the educational system. The number of women who used to receive general literary and cultural education must have been fairly large. For a long time family was the only educational institution, and even boys used to receive education only from their fathers or elders. The same naturally was the case with girls. But in later times a class of women teachers came to being (Upadhyayani). There was no purdah custom in Hindu society down to the 12th century, and so there was no difficulty for women in taking to the teaching profession. Lady teachers may probably have confined themselves to the teaching of girl-students. Panini refers to boarding houses for lady-students, *chhatrisalas*, and these probably were under the care of lady teachers.

Co-education was also prevalent in ancient India in mild form. Sometimes boys and girls were educated together while receiving higher education. From the 'Malatimadhava' of Bhavabhuti, written in the 8th century A.D., we learn that the nun Kamandaki was educated along with Bhurivasu and Devarata at a famous centre of education. In the 'Uttara-Rama-charit also (of the same author) we find Atreyi receiving her education along with Kusa and Lava.

It is difficult to determine the exact extent of education imparted to women during the early Vedic period in India. Upanayana ritual was obligatory for girls, and this must have ensured the imparting of a certain amount of Vedic and literary education to the girls of all classes. But female education received a great set-back during later Vedic period primarily owing to the decline of the religious status of women.

Upanayana began to be gradually prohibited to girls and by about 500 B.C. it had already become a formality. The discontinuance of Upanayana was disastrous to the religious status of women and they were declared unfit to recite Vedic Mantras and perform Vedic sacrifices. Thus Vedic education was prohibited to women. With the advent of foreigners the Brahmanical society became rigid and conservative.

The pandits adopted measures of defence. For this the women lost their freedom. They were confined within the home. In the changed situation the right to study came to be denied to women. With the code of Manu (200 A.D.) (Manusmriti or Manusanghita) her dependent position was firmly established. According to Manu, "by a girl, by a young woman, or even by an aged one, nothing must be done independently". Manu further opines that "in childhood a female must be subject to her father, in youth to her husband, when her lord is dead to her sons", a woman must never be independent. Irrespective of time whether it is day or night a women must be kept in dependence by the males of their families. Her father protects her in childhood, her husband protects her in youth, and her sons protect her in old age; a woman is never fit for independence". Thus, at the time of Manu, women were in low esteem and were not allowed to study the Vedas. Early marriage had become by now the custom.

The trouble caused by the discontinuance of Upanayana was further enhanced by the lowering of the marriageable age. In the Vedic period, girls were married at about the age of 16 or 17; but in the later Vedic period (from 500 B.C to 500 A.D.) girls were married at the age of 8 or 9. Early marriage of girls gave a death-blow to female education. Though in society, as a whole, female education received a great set-back during this period, it continued to receive attention in rich, aristocratic and royal families. Girls in these families were given a fairly good literary education but surely not Vedic literature.

The only education a girl of an ordinary family received was one which fitted her to fulfil her duties in the household of her husband. Her duties mainly confined to rearing up her children, keeping everything clean, preparing food for the members of the family and looking after the household utensils. Thus, the education of girls was entirely domestic. They used to receive education at homes.

Women in India were deprived of educational privileges for centuries, but there were always some exceptions to this general condition. Indian literature of all ages refers to educated women who took prominent part even in public affairs and showed finest skill in fine arts as well as in military art. Chandragupta Maurya had women bodyguards.

As we have mentioned earlier, the daughters of princes and well-to-do families often received some education from their fathers or elders or family priests. Many female ascetics and mendicants used to learn some Sanskrit and were conversant with popular religious poems.

The dancing girls in the South who often were attached to temples (devadasis) received some education, particularly in dancing and music. They were famous for their wit and cleverness. These semi-prostitutes learnt to read, sing and dance. These prostitutes sometimes worked as spies. The education of prostitutes is a very ancient custom in India. The Arthashastra of Kautilya refers to the education of the prostitutes.

Buddhism no doubt had its effect on the education of women. The Buddhist monastic order included not only monks but also nuns (bhikshunis). But it was only with the greatest reluctance that the Buddha consented to this arrangement. In this he no doubt reflected the opinions of his time which were against the independence and education of women.

His aunt, Mahaprajapati, expressed her desire to join the order, but he refused thrice. At last, at the fervent appeal of Ananda, his first and favourite disciple, the Buddha yielded. He, however, expressed his sorrow and opined that the admission of women would ruin his work. The nuns were made closely dependent on the monks, and could only be admitted by them.

There are ample evidences to show that the Buddha, like Manu, shared the low opinion of women. It is true that Buddhist nunneries did not spread to a desirable extent. Their number was very few. The cause is very simple. The Buddhist movement gave only an indirect impetus to female education. Nunneries were not in vogue by the end of 4th century A.D. Chinese pilgrims of the 5th and 7th centuries. A.D. do not refer to them at all.

It is interesting to note that in modern Ceylon (Sri Lanka) and Burma (Myanmar) nuns are very small in number compared with the monks. In these countries nunneries do not impart instructions to girls as monasteries do to boys. This shows that Buddhist nunneries did not help much to spread education amongst women. There is nothing to show that the nunneries, like the monasteries, became centres of general education.

Even when Buddhism was at its zenith in India it did very little for the education of women. But those nuns who joined the order received instruction in the Buddhist doctrines and also in reading and writing. No doubt some attained to higher proficiency in learning. There are numerous references in Buddhist literature to the intellectual attainments of many Buddhist nuns. Some of them even became famous as teachers and scholars.

Women Education in Medieval India

As by passage of time, the position of women became worse in medieval period, rather to develop some good changes in their status. During the medieval period only, system of Purdah and Jauhar were being introduced by Muslim and Rajput community against woman. Firstly 'Purdah' means, woman in Muslim community is fully covered with clothes, so as to cover their body from male. Secondly 'Jauhar' means, woman with their own consent immolate themselves so as to save

their body and property from detention of enemy, if they are from defeated Warriors family. In both the systems, liberty of woman was curtailed by the community that they were not giving right to moment or leave their lives without any restriction of fear and without any burden. Despite all these religious restrictions, women at that time actively participated in social, political educational and religious field like Raziya Sultan who was first lady Monarch of Delhi, Chand Bibi who has defeated Akbar etc. in this period too, bhakti moment had played a very important role for improvement and impoverishment of the status of woman. These were the movement which tried to give equal status to women in society at that time. The best example, who preaches the equality of men and women at that time, was a 'Guru Nanak'. He advocates equality of women in each sector that is religious, political, educational and cultural

Women Education in Modern India

In ancient and medieval period status of woman is practically lower than the male but the in scripture; theoretically it has given higher status to woman. They are awarded with degree of perfect home maker by the society, because Indian woman have dedicated their whole life for welfare and wellbeing of their families. They are also praying by human being in the form of goddess. Still no change is there in their status. They are treated inferior as it is. As we all know that, it's a human nature, if they want some powerful things, they always pray to goddess in the form of 'Devi' but, if the woman who exist in their life as mother, sister and wife, they do not treat her like this or treat like a slave in their family, who works 24 hours for them without expecting anything. This position become worse, when she gave birth to girl child in educated or uneducated family after devoting her all possible efforts to her family

But the position and status of today's Woman in India is considerably changed in modern Indian Society. The population of woman is almost half of the total population of India. A country or a community cannot be considered civilized where woman is not honored. Indian Laws are being made without discrimination against woman, as a result Indian woman enjoying high position in our society. Woman today occupy high ranking posts like I.A.S., I.P.S., also in our Defense Services. The modern Indian woman participate in various sports and games like football, hockey, cricket, table tennis, lawn tennis and also in athletics namely Saniya Mirza, Sayana Nehawal etc. The Contemporary Indian women serve as M.P., M.L.A, Governors and Ministers. Women of recent times like Mother Teresa, Soniya Gandhi, Vijay Lakshmi Pandit, M.S. Subhalakshmi, Lata Mangeskar and our ex-president of India Pratibhatai Patil have achieved International fame. Women have also achieved high fame in the areas of literature, music and acting.

The main reason for lag in women education is in traditional Indian society sons are considered as assets while girls are considered as liability so spending on their education is not considered as a priority. As per the traditional Indian society the role of woman in society is only to look after house and children which does not require any schooling. There is concern that if woman is educated, then she will start earning and will become independent which might hurt the ego of a male. The structure of Indian society is patriarchal in which everything revolves around male and woman is reduced to negligible role. In poor families, the girl child has to look after her siblings as well as do household chores so she could not have luxury of money and time to spend on education.

Advantages of Women Education to the Society

The advantages of women education mainly leads to social development, women education will help to solve many issues faced by society. Kothari commission of 1968 recommended education as tool for social development. By pacing woman education India can achieve the goal of social development.

It also ensures gender equality that is women is part of unprivileged section of society. Education will help to close a gender gap in society. Co-education institutes will help children to give respect to female.

It increase the economic productivity it will bring economic gains not only to women but will also raise GDP of a nation

It also reduce infant mortality rate, a well educated woman will have more chances of making better decisions for her family's health. Studies have shown that increased literacy among woman will bring down infant mortality rate.

It improves the standard of living, education will improve chances of employment for a women. A well educated woman has more chances of getting better employment and better standard of living.

Increase inclusive growth of a society, as a developing nation India strives for growth in each sector for all sections of society and education is a way to achieve this goal.

It increase women empowerment that means education is powerful tool for woman emancipation and empowerment. For long woman has been deprived of her rights. By educating herself she can achieve a place in society. It also strengthening the democracy as education will create awareness among woman which will cause increased participation in politics which ultimately leads to strengthening of democracy. They could secure their rights through mobilization.

Main Government Schemes to Encourage Women Education

Sakshar bharat mission for female literacy: Launched in 2008 for promoting adult education especially among woman under which Lok Shiksha Kendras were set up.

SABLA-Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls: It aims to provide nutrition for growing adolescent girls by provision of food grains.

Right to Education: RTE considers education as a fundamental right which will provide free and compulsory education to every child aged between 6 to 14.

Kasturba Balika Vidyalaya- :Establishment of residential upper primary schools for girl

National Programme for Education of Girls at Elementary Level: It is for reduction in the school dropouts by giving special attention to weak girls. In villages, women's group are formed. These groups follow up/supervision on girl's enrollment, attendance.

Mahila Sangha: Under this scheme women's forums (Mahila Sangha) were created. It provides space for rural women to meet, discuss issues, ask questions, make informed choices. It is implemented in ten states.

Rahstriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan: Infrastructure for girls hostel for secondary education

Dhanlakshmi scheme: Conditional money transfer scheme for Girl Child following 3 conditions.

1. At birth and Registration of Birth.
2. Progress of Immunization and Completion of Immunization.
3. Enrollment and Retention in School.

Conclusion

The acceptance by educated women of an insulting institution like dowry indicates that our womenfolk have never examined the real meaning of the constitutional and legal guarantees. An educated woman is like a magic wand which brings prosperity, health and pride. We just have to unleash her potential and see the magic happen. We have improved a lot on women education since our independence, but still a lot remains to be improved. Factors restricting the growth of women education in India are mainly societal, and we need to recognize them and eliminate them, if we want to achieve the goals of socio-economic development.

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